

ONLINE QUIZ EXAM PORTAL

Sadhvi D Alva¹

Mohammed Aiman²

Mohammed Zaid³

Ajmal Abdul Rahiman⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Student, Dept. of Information Science & Engineering

Divyashree S⁵

⁵Assistant Professor, Dept. of Information Science & Engineering
Mangalore Institute of Technology & Engineering, Moodabidri, India

Abstract:- A web-based quiz system for students is the Online Quiz System. It is a framework by which understudies can sit in a test which need no pencil and paper. Today, students take quizzes by hand. Grading should take up more time in lectures. other than that, the test paper perhaps absent. To receive their results, students must wait for lecturers to finish grading. Because of the automated marking, assist in improving lecturers save time because lecturers can set up quizzes that will automatically grade themselves. Students can obtain their results promptly by answering the quiz from anywhere. This online quiz system interprets data in a useful manner by employing a rule-based algorithm. This system uses a short answer based on a keyword rule-based algorithm. The Quiz Portal can serve as an alternative to the conventional paper-and-pencil examinations provided by numerous institutions. Quiz Portal makes learning enjoyable and simple. Multiple-choice questions can be utilized irregular or surprise tests through this system. It delivers results immediately, saving time. The test papers and the specific questions will be created, modified, and deleted by the administrator. The applicant can enlist, login and give the test with his special id and can consider the outcome to be well.

Keywords:- Online Examination, Systematic Literature Review, Exam Creation, Analyse Response.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 'Online Test Application' venture will be created to defeat the tedious issue of manual framework. In addition, the examiners' time is wasted by the current system when they check the answer sheets after the test. This application will check for the correct answer, save the examiners' time, and conduct the exam effectively. The clients which are utilize this framework don't have to high figuring information and furthermore framework will illuminate them while entering invalid information. The current manual system will be computerized as part of this project, allowing examiners to save valuable time and data. In addition, the system's information will remain readily available for an extended duration and be easily accessible. This task assists the inspectors with dealing with their administrations positively and offer a superior support to their clients. In

addition to its administrative component, we plan to provide support for a variety of users as part of the project's design and implementation.

➤ Scope of Project

This project covers a wide range of other manual examinations. A small number of them are applicable in both the business and educational sectors. Can be accessed anytime since it is a digital application (user area doesn't make any difference). No limitation that inspector must be available when the applicant steps through the exam. Plan to work with head and client online assessment is intended for instructive establishments like schools, school and confidential organizations to direct rationale trial of their understudies on normal premise. When compared to other exams, the online examination system is widely used. Online assessment framework can be utilized in confidential foundations as well as instructive organization. It can be used anywhere and at any time due to its user-friendly web base application.

➤ Objectives

The fundamental target of the undertaking MCQ Test Application is to deal with the subtleties of understudies, assessments, stamps, courses and papers. Because the project is entirely at the administrative end, only the administrator has access. The project's objective is to progress a software that will make managing MCQ quizzes easier without requiring as much manual labor as possible. To create a robust framework for optimal handling of MCQ content. To beat the tedious issues and taking MCQ tests. To provide the test taker with their marks as soon as possible. To deal with the data of various tests.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Literature survey a literature survey takes into account the project's various parameters and scope to present the different forms of analyses and research conducted in the area of interest in addition to those previously published results. It includes the methodology of various analysts' research in addition to their conclusions. Because it provides the research's direction, it is the report's most crucial section.

➤ *Background Studies*

The undertaking: The "Online Quiz Exam Portal" contains a collection of various quizzes. The user can take the test and access the entire quiz. Each user will receive credit score for e correct response to a limited number of questions. There are numerous quizzes apps available online. However, there are a few that help users better understand each other and the application, such as answering questions correctly, resolving user queries, uploading questions with answers, and so on. Entrepreneurship when handled appropriately. Home cooking is by all accounts a pattern which might continue in years to come. Home cooking was seen as a long-term opportunity and a sustainable, profitable business when the pandemic struck. Even though everyone was affected by COVID-19, it seems to have been good for home cooks, not just in the short term but also in the long run.

➤ *Systems in use now*

• *Test Up:*

Quiz Up is a social network and trivia game that lets you post about your interest¹, participate in challenges and illustrated quizzes, and choose from more than 1,200 topics. You can compete with your acquaintances or millions of other users of the platform.

• *A Word of Caution:*

This family-friendly game has players guessing words, names, and titles from their friends' descriptions or recitations of famous people, characters, movies, books, and songs. Simply consider it pretenses for the cell phone age.

• *Who Would Like to be Rich:*

You can now relive the thrilling buildup as you to become a (virtual) millionaire in the classic game that has attempt won over audiences all over the world. Feat1u0res can also play against family and friends. include 50:50, ask the audience, and ask the expert.

• *Popcorn Facts:*

Try out your insight into the cinema with this habit-forming film random data application. Questions, in light of exemplary movies, blockbusters and fan top picks, range picture adjusts and numerous decisions. Each question is followed with an intriguing truth. Play alone or with others

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Online examinations are conducted with this application. The questions must be given to the students, who can sit at their own terminals and log in to take the exam in the allotted time. This application will correct, immediately display the result, and store it in a database. The administrator can easily add new tests with this application. This application lets the instructor add questions to the exam and change the questions on a specific exam. This application deals with confirmation of the chairman, Educator as well as the understudy.

➤ *The features of the online test created for online testing are as follows:*

- *The proposed system will be more effective and take less time to implement than the current one.*
- *Because the simulator itself calculates and evaluates, the result will be extremely precise and accurate and will be announced quickly.*
- *Because the proposed system is solely dependent on the administrator, there is no risk of question paper leakage.*
- *The logs of seemed competitors and their imprints are put away and can be reinforcement for some time later*

IV. FRAMEWORK REQUIREMENT

A framework examination is a portrayal of a product framework to be created. It specifies both the software's functional and non-functional requirements, and it may also include a set of use cases outlining the user interactions that the software must support.

A. *A Requirement for use*

The main objective of the system should be to provide an easy-to-understand and user-friendly interface that anyone can use. System feature:

➤ *A functional requirement for the online Quiz is provided in this section. There are two modules in this stage:*

- *Student/Client Module.*
- *Admin Module*

➤ *Usefulness of Every Module are:*

User/student module: The student or user must sign in to the application. They can take any of the quizzes. The student or user will then receive the results as soon as the test is finished.

➤ *Admin Section:*

The administrator can see every one of the tables in the Data set and can add the Inquiry by choosing the specific subject.

B. *Requirement Not Required For Use*

Quality characteristics of a system that are used to evaluate the system's operation and performance.

Execution necessities reaction time-

The framework will give reactions in 2 sec after client login. Requirements for safety include the safe storage of all logged information, updates, and user actions.

Security Requirement: The system administrator must synchronize any database modifications

C. *Software Requirements*

The Software prerequisites for the project development are as follows

- Operating System: Windows 10
- Front End: HTML, CSS
- Back End: Java
- IDE : Visual Studio
- Database: My SQL

D. Hardware Requirements

Following shows the Hardware requirements for development of the project.

- Processor : Intel(R) Core™ i3-6006U CPU@2.00GHz
- Hard Disk : 160GB
- Memory : 4GB

E. Summary

In this system requirements, we have discussed the Functional requirements to identify the use cases involved and sketch UML diagrams for the use cases identified which includes Activity diagrams and Sequence diagrams. Simultaneously, we discuss the Non-Functional requirement which provides quality attributes of a system used to judge operation of a system and also ensure the performance of the system.

Finally, we conclude the chapter with hardware and software requirements which lists out the software used to build the application and the tools involved to incorporate the software application employed for implementing.

V. RESULTS AND DESCRIPTION

➤ Signup Page

Fig 1 The UI Screens Completed for the web Application.

➤ Administrator Login Page

Fig 2 Admin Login Page

The system's admin login page can be found here. Users should sign in to. To make sure, that the login module is safe from hackers, JavaScript validation was used.

➤ Page for Teacher Signup

Fig 3 Teacher Signup Page

This is the information exchange page for educator in the framework. The teacher should enter their credentials to join the system.

➤ Page For Student Login

Fig 4 Student Login Page

The system's sign-up page for students is here. The understudy ought to join to the framework by entering his/her accreditations.

➤ Admin Page

Fig 5 Admin Page

The admin page is used to manage the entire exam process, including creating and editing quizzes, managing user accounts, setting up exam rules and guidelines, monitoring exam performance, and generating reports. The admin pages is usually accessible only to authorized individuals who are accountable for ensuring that operations run seamlessly of the online exam platform.

VI. CONCLUSION

The online quiz exam portal project is an important and useful tool for educational institutions and organizations to manage and conduct exams online. This project can provide numerous benefits, including increased efficiency, reduced costs.

One of the main advantages of an online quiz exam portal is the ability to conduct exams remotely, which can save time and resources for both exam takers and administrators. This also allows for a greater number of participants to take the exam, as it is not limited by physical space or location.

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